

STRESS WAVE PROPAGATION IN LAMINATED COMPOSITES
HAVING VISCO-ELASTIC ADHESIVE LAYERS

Toru Fujii*, Sadao Amijima** and Mamoru Maenaka**

* 4th Research Center, Technical Research and Development Inst.
Japan Defense Agency Kanagawa Japan

** Faculty of Engineering, Doshisha Univ. Kyoto Japan

This paper deals with the stress wave propagation in two layered laminated composites which consist of two different kinds of materials. They were bonded together with an adhesive having visco-elastic properties. When one end of the composites are subjected to an impact loading, the resulting stress wave propagates in each layer changing its shape and causes the adhesive shear stress. These phenomena are investigated experimentally by the shock tube apparatus and theoretically by the finite element method. For the stress wave profile in each layer, good agreements are found between experimental and theoretical results.

Introduction

When an impact loading is applied to one end of composite materials, the resulting stress wave propagates in them. The phenomena of the stress wave propagation are very complex because they consist of different materials whose stress wave speeds are different.

Studies on the phenomena of the stress wave propagation in alternatively laminated composites which consist of two different kinds of materials are presented. Two rods with uniform cross-section but different elastic properties are bonded together with an adhesive. When such two layered laminated composite is subjected to the impact loading at one end, the resulting stress wave propagates in each layer changing its shape and causes the bond shear stress in the adhesive layer. Dynamic bond shear stresses and axial stress wave profiles in the layered materials(rod) are studied experimentally and numerically. The finite element method taking account of the effect of the adhesive layer and its visco-elastic characteristics based on a weighted residual method is applied to the numerical analysis.

Equation of Motion

Two kinds of elastic rods are bonded alternatively to form a laminated composite. When the impact loading is applied to one end of the laminated composite as shown in Fig.1, the resulting longitudinal elastic stress waves propagate parallel to the layers.

Fig.2 shows the schematic view of the simplified model of the laminated composite. It is assumed that the stress and the strain are uniformly distributed over each of the rod cross-sections and act solely in the axial

Fig.1 Alternatively laminated composite

Fig.2 Two layered composite model

direction. Transverse displacements from Poisson effects and the effect of bending are neglected. The analysis is simplified further by neglecting of the adhesive inertia.

An element of the composite, located at a distance x from the loaded end, is shown in Fig.3. Each layer has a Young's modulus E , mass density ρ , cross-sectional area A and axial displacement $u(x,t)$, where t is time. Lower subscripts 1 and 2 identify the layered materials 1 and 2, respectively. The adhesive layer has a thickness b and width w . All the material properties as well as the cross-sectional area, are assumed to be uniform along the axis. It is assumed that the visco-elastic properties of the adhesive is represented by the Voigt model(Fig.4).

Fig.3 Stress components acting on a two layered element

Fig.4 Voigt model

From the Voigt model assumption, the bond shear stress τ in the adhesive layer is given as follow.

$$\tau = G\gamma + \eta\dot{\gamma} \quad (1)$$

where G is the rigidity of the Voigt model and η is the damping coefficient. γ represents the shear strain of the adhesive layer and it is defined by the following expression.

$$\gamma = \frac{u_2 - u_1}{b} \quad (2)$$

The axial stress σ is related to the axial strain by Hook's law.

$$\sigma_1 = E_1 \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial x}, \quad \sigma_2 = E_2 \frac{\partial u_2}{\partial x} \quad (3)$$

For an element, summation of forces in the axial direction in each layer gives the following one dimensional equations of motion.

$$E_1 A_1 \frac{\partial^2 u_1}{\partial x^2} + wG \frac{u_2 - u_1}{b} + w\eta \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{u_2 - u_1}{b} \right) = A_1 \rho_1 \frac{\partial^2 u_1}{\partial t^2} \quad (4)$$

$$E_2 A_2 \frac{\partial^2 u_2}{\partial x^2} - wG \frac{u_2 - u_1}{b} - w\eta \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{u_2 - u_1}{b} \right) = A_2 \rho_2 \frac{\partial^2 u_2}{\partial t^2} \quad (5)$$

Matrix notations can reduce the above equations into

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_1 E_1 & 0 \\ 0 & A_2 E_2 \end{bmatrix} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \{u\} - \frac{wG}{b} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \{u\} - w\eta \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \{\dot{u}\} = \begin{bmatrix} A_1 \rho_1 & 0 \\ 0 & A_2 \rho_2 \end{bmatrix} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \{u\}$$

where

$$\{u\}^T = [u_1, u_2]$$

(6)

Finite Element Analysis

Fig.5 shows the space region divided into finite elements. Consider the element i . For the layered materials 1 and 2, the displacements of the nodal point i at a time t are as follows.

$$u_1^i = u_1^i(0, t), \quad u_2^i = u_2^i(0, t) \quad (7)$$

The displacements of the nodal point $i+1$ at the same time are

$$u_1^{i+1} = u_1^{i+1}(L, t), \quad u_2^{i+1} = u_2^{i+1}(L, t) \quad (8)$$

where upper subscripts identify the nodal points and L is the length of the finite element.

Fig.5 Finite element division

It is assumed that the displacements in the element are interpolated linearly with each nodal displacement.

$$u_1 = \frac{L-x}{L} u_1 + \frac{x}{L} u_2 \quad (9)$$

$$u_2 = \frac{L-x}{L} u_2 + \frac{x}{L} u_1 \quad (10)$$

Using local co-ordinate systems L_1 and L_2 , the above equations are rewritten as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} L_1 & 0 & L_2 & 0 \\ 0 & L_1 & 0 & L_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} u_1^i \\ u_2^i \\ u_1^{i+1} \\ u_2^{i+1} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

$$= [N] \{d\}$$

where

$$L_1 = \frac{L-x}{L}, \quad L_2 = \frac{x}{L}$$

$$[N] = \begin{bmatrix} L_1 & 0 & L_2 & 0 \\ 0 & L_1 & 0 & L_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\{d\} = [u_1^i, u_2^i, u_1^{i+1}, u_2^{i+1}]$$

Similarly, the velocity and the acceleration are given by

$$\frac{d}{dt} \{u\} = [N] \frac{d}{dt} \{d\}, \quad \frac{d^2}{dt^2} \{u\} = [N] \frac{d^2}{dt^2} \{d\} \quad (12)$$

By letting the weighting function $[W] = [N]$, following Galarkin's integral for each finite element is obtained.

$$\int_x [W] \left(\begin{bmatrix} A_1 \rho_1 & 0 \\ 0 & A_2 \rho_2 \end{bmatrix} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \{u\} - \begin{bmatrix} A_1 E_1 & 0 \\ 0 & A_2 E_2 \end{bmatrix} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \{u\} + \frac{wG}{b} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \{u\} + w\eta \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \{u\} \right) dx = 0 \quad (13)$$

Integral is limited within an element. Equation (13) gives the simultaneous finite element equations of motion as follow.

$$[m] \frac{d^2}{dt^2} \{u\} + [c] \frac{d}{dt} \{u\} + ([k_m] + [k_a]) \{u\} = \{f\} \quad (14)$$

Where, $[m]$ is the element mass matrix, $[c]$ is the element damping matrix, $[k_m]$ and $[k_a]$ are the element stiffness matrices related to the layered materials and the adhesive layer, respectively.

The element mass matrix $[m]$ is given as

$$[m] = \frac{L}{6} \begin{bmatrix} 2A_1 \rho_1 & & & & \text{Sym.} \\ 0 & 2A_2 \rho_2 & & & \\ A_1 \rho_1 & 0 & 2A_1 \rho_1 & & \\ 0 & A_2 \rho_2 & 0 & 2A_2 \rho_2 & \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

The element damping matrix $[c]$ is given as

$$[c] = \frac{w\eta L}{6b} \begin{bmatrix} 2 & & & & \text{Sym.} \\ -2 & 2 & & & \\ 1 & -1 & 2 & & \\ -1 & 1 & -2 & 2 & \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

The element stiffness matrices $[k_m]$ and $[k_a]$ are

$$[k_m] = \frac{1}{L} \begin{bmatrix} A_1 E_1 & & & & \text{Sym.} \\ 0 & A_2 E_2 & & & \\ -A_1 E_1 & 0 & & A_1 E_1 & \\ 0 & -A_2 E_2 & 0 & & A_2 E_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad [k_a] = \frac{wGL}{6b} \begin{bmatrix} 2 & & & \text{Sym.} \\ -2 & 2 & & \\ 1 & -1 & 2 & \\ -1 & 1 & -2 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

Experiment

In order to avoid the effect of bending, the specimen having three layers (Copper/Aluminum/Copper) shown in Fig.6 was used in the experiment. After surfacing treatment, the specimen was bonded for two hours at 80°C in an oven with Araldite AW106. The length of the specimen is 400mm and the adhesive thickness is 1mm. Semi-conductor strain gages (Kyowa KSP-2-E4) were mounted on each layer as shown in Fig.6. In the experiment, a loading with

Fig.6 Dimensions of the specimen

Fig.7 Shock tube experimental apparatus

an abrupt increase in pressure approximating a step function was produced with a shock tube by reflection of a normal shock wave of the surface of the end of the specimen. The experimental apparatus is shown in Fig.7. The pressure step remained constant for a time t on the order of milliseconds. The details of its utilization for obtaining dynamic properties of materials are included in references (1) and (2).

The resulting stress waves in each layer are observed with the strain gages. It is more important to know the bond shear stress in the adhesive layer, however, it is impossible to measure it directly. Therefore, only the strain-time history of each layer was measured.

Results and Discussion

Experimental result

Fig.8 shows the stress(strain) wave records in the Copper and Aluminum layers of the specimen under step pressure loading produced with the shock tube. Upper and lower records in the figure show the strain-time histories in each layer at distances $x=40\text{mm}$ and $x=200\text{mm}$ from the impact end, respectively. At $x=40\text{mm}$, there is a time lag of the arrived stress in the Copper layer. The strain in the Aluminum layer appears first, then, the strain in the Copper layer appears after some time intervals. The time lag at $x=200\text{mm}$ is longer than that at $x=40\text{mm}$. Furthermore, the strain in the Aluminum layer appears only at $x=200\text{mm}$, after then it vanishes once. However, it appears again with the strain in the Copper layer. These time lags are dependent on the differences of the stress wave speeds. The speed of the Copper is lower than the Aluminum one. Therefore, the strain in the Aluminum layer is always detected at first by the strain gages. The comparison between the experiment and the numerical results is discussed below. The moderate oscillations were observed in both strain records after the strains had abruptly risen. It is considered that the effect of bending appeared because the strain gages were mounted on one side of the specimen.

Fig.8 Strain records of the specimen obtained by the experiment

Numerical result

In Fig.9 to 16, the results of the numerical analysis by the finite element method are shown. The laminated composite model is divided equally into 200 elements for the numerical analysis. In order to integrate the simultaneous differential equation (14), Newmark's β method was used, where the value β was $1/6$. The examples of two kinds of loading applied to the end of the model were calculated. One is a pressure loading and another is a velocity loading. The material properties and dimensions of the model for calculations are given in Table 1.

(1) Pressure pulse loading

Fog.9 to 11 show the numerical results under step pressure pulse loading. Pressure P_0 (see Fig.2) is 0.5kg/mm^2 . This condition is approximately the

Table 1 Material properties and dimensions of the model

Material 1 (Aluminum)	Young's modulus	$E_1 = 7000 \text{ kg/mm}^2$
	Specific gravity	$\gamma_1 = 2.8 \text{ g/cm}^3$
	Height	$h_1 = 1.5 \text{ mm}$
Material 2 (Copper)	Young's modulus	$E_2 = 12500 \text{ kg/mm}^2$
	Specific gravity	$\gamma_2 = 8.9 \text{ g/cm}^3$
	Height	$h_2 = 3.0 \text{ mm}$
Adhesive	Rigidity	$G = 50 \text{ kg/mm}^2$
	Damping coefficient	$\eta = 0 \text{ kg}\mu\text{s/mm}^2$
		$= 19$
		$= 190$
	Thickness	$b = 1 \text{ mm}$

Fig.9 Numerical results for the case without the damping ($\eta=0$) under step pressure pulse loading

same as the experiment except for the pressure level. Fig.9-1 to 9-3 show the strain-time histories in each layer and the bond shear stress-time histories at the distances $x=0, 40$ and 200mm , respectively. In this case, η is zero. The adhesive layer is elastic and it has no strain rate sensitivities.

Comparing the profiles of the strain-time histories of the numerical results with the experimental one, good agreements are found. Fig.9-4 and 9-5 show the strain distributions in each layer and the bond shear stress distributions at a time $t=20$ and $60 \mu\text{sec}$, respectively. It is found that the maximum bond shear stress occurs at the loaded end. It decreases rapidly as the distance from the end increases. The second peak of the bond shear stress is seen near the wave front in the Copper layer. These results coincide with the theoretical results obtained by R.G.Payton using Laplace transforms.³

Fig.10 Numerical results for the case with the damping ($\eta=19\text{kgus/mm}^2$) under step pressure pulse loading

In general, adhesives have visco-elastic mechanical properties, i.e., strain rate sensitivities⁴. The observed stiffness of the adhesive layer changes as the strain rate changes⁵. Even without the damping, the bond shear stress is not constant and it decays gradually as oscillating sinusoidally. Consequently, the shear strain of the adhesive layer changes with time and also the shear strain rate is not constant. Therefore, if the adhesive has visco-elastic characteristics, the behavior of the stress wave propagation is different from the case with no damping.

Fig. 10 shows the calculated results of the case with the damping ($\eta=19$ kgus/mm²). Comparing Fig.10 with Fig.9, There are significant differences between them. For example, the oscillation of the bond shear stress at the impact end in the case with the damping decays more rapidly than in the case without the damping, and the oscillation can not be found in the trace any

Fig.11 Numerical results for the case with the damping ($\eta=190\text{kgus/mm}^2$) under step pressure pulse loading

more at the time $60\mu\text{sec}$. Critical numerical results were obtained for the case with the damping ($\eta=190\text{kg}\mu\text{s}/\text{mm}^2$) as shown in Fig.11. There is no oscillation in the bond shear stress-time traces. Immediately after the impact, the maximum shear stress occurs and it decays rapidly and uniformly.

The dynamic bond shear stress is caused by the difference of stress wave speeds and its level depends not only on mechanical properties of each composition and dimensions but also on the pulse risetime of the applied pressure. An example of the ramp type pressure pulse with a risetime $T=20\mu\text{sec}$ applied to the model is calculated. Fig.12 shows the numerical results of the case under ramp pulse loading, where the adhesive damping η is zero. In comparison with the example under step pressure pulse loading, it is found that the maximum bond shear stress and its second peak are very lower than those under step pressure pulse loading.

Fig.13 shows the relation between the maximum bond shear stress and the pulse risetime. The dotted line in the figure denotes the maximum bond shear stress under static loading, which occurs at the loaded end. The maximum bond shear stress in the case with the damping ($\eta=190\text{kg}\mu\text{s}/\text{mm}^2$) under step pressure pulse loading occurs 10mm from the impact end. However, in most cases except the case above mentioned, it occurs at the impact end. The influence of the pulse risetime on the maximum bond shear stress in the case with the damping ($\eta=19\text{kg}\mu\text{s}/\text{mm}$) is similar to in the case with no damping. However, in the case with the damping ($\eta=190\text{kg}\mu\text{s}/\text{mm}$), the influence is much different from the others. In any cases, the maximum bond shear stress under impact loading approaches the value under static loading, as the pulse risetime increases.

Fig. 12 Numerical results for the case with no damping under ramp type pressure pulse loading (pulse risetime $T=20\mu\text{sec}$)

Fig.13 Relation between the pulse risetime and the maximum bond shear stress under pressure pulse loading

(2) Velocity pulse loading

As the impact loading applied at the end of the laminated composite model, the corresponding velocity pulse loading can be considered. Several examples under velocity pulse loading (step and ramp) applied to the end of the model are calculated.

Fig.14 shows the numerical results under step velocity pulse loading where the velocity V_0 is 2.5m/sec. Fig.14-1 to 14-3 show the strain-time histories in each layer and the bond shear stress-time histories at the distances $x=0, 40$ and 200mm , respectively. Fig.14-4 and 14-5 show the strain distributions and the bond shear stress distributions at the time $t=20$ and $60\mu\text{sec}$. From these figures, it is found that the values of the strain in each layer become the same everywhere except at each wave front, they correspond with the value calculated by 'Rule of Mixture' considering the model as a composite. The maximum bond shear stress occurs when the wave front in the Copper layer passes over a distance $x=40\text{mm}$ from the impact end. The shear stress at the impact end is always zero because the relative displacement between two layers does not exist.

As well as in the case under pressure pulse loading, The ramp type velocity pulse loading can be considered. Fig.15 shows the numerical results of the case under ramp pulse loading. The pulse risetime is also $20\mu\text{sec}$. It is found that the strains in each layer become the same value everywhere, more so than in the case under step pulse loading. The bond shear stress is very low, and it occurs only at the ramp. The bond shear stress disappears after the ramp of the pulse passes away. From these figures, it is more apparent than in the case under pressure pulse loading, that the bond shear stress is caused by the differences of the stress wave speeds and their propagations.

Fig.16 shows the relation between the maximum bond shear stress and the pulse risetime. In this case, the damping of the adhesive does not exist. The maximum bond shear stress decreases rapidly as the risetime becomes longer, and it becomes zero at last. Under static loading, where the constrained

displacement is applied to the ends of the model, no bond shear stress occurs in the model. In addition, the distance where the maximum bond shear stress occurs depends on the pulse risetime.

Fig.14 Numerical results for the case with no damping under step velocity pulse loading

Fig.15 Numerical results for the case with no damping under ramp type velocity loading (pulse risetime $T=20\mu\text{sec}$)

Fig.16 Relation between the pulse risetime and the maximum bond shear stress in the case with no damping under velocity pulse loading.

Conclusions

The phenomena of the stress wave propagation in two layered laminated composites having visco-elastic adhesive layers have been investigated, where various kinds of impact loadings are applied to one end of the composites. It was found that the maximum bond shear stress occurred at the impact end or near the impact end under pressure pulse loading, and the second peak of the bond shear stress appeared near the wave front. It was also found from the numerical analysis by the finite element method, that the maximum bond shear stress level depended on the pulse risetime and visco-elastic properties of the adhesive. Under velocity pulse loading, the bond shear stress appears at the wave front as the stress wave propagates and it is always zero at the impact end. These bond shear stresses are caused by the differences of the stress wave speeds. Furthermore, good agreements were found between the numerical results and the experimental one when the step pressure pulse loading was applied to the end of the laminated composite model.

References

1. Glass, I. I. and Patterson, G. N., "A Theoretical and Experimental Study of Shock Tube Flow," J. Aero. Sci., Vol.22, No.2, 1955, P.73
2. Davis, H. J. and Curchack, H. D., "Shock Tube Techniques and Instrumentation," TR-1429 [Harry Diamond Laboratory] 1969
3. Payton, R. G., "Dynamic Bond Stress in a Composite structure Subjected to a Sudden Pressure Rise," J. Appl. Mech., ASME, 1965, P.643
4. Fujii, T., Amino, H. and Amijima, S., "Dynamic Response of Adhesive Joints" Proceedings of the 20th Japan Congress on Materials Research, 1977, P.110
5. Fujii, T. and Amijima, S., "The Effect of Strain Rate on Mechanical Properties of Adhesives and Adhesive Bonded Joints," International Conference on Fracture Mechanics and Technology, 3C-5, March, 1977